

**TYPES OF EDITING OF A LITERARY TEXT: STYLISTIC,
COMPOSITIONAL, LINGUISTIC**

Yulduz Uktamovna Ishmatova

Senior Lecturer, Senior Lecturer, Tashkent Region Branch of Astrakhan State
Technical University, Uzbekistan

Abstract

The article discusses the types of editing of literary texts - stylistic, compositional and linguistic editing. The process of editing literary works is important in ensuring that the text is clear, fluent and effective. Stylistic editing is aimed at adapting the text to stylistic or lexical rules, compositional editing is aimed at harmonizing the structure and parts of the text, and linguistic editing is aimed at correcting grammatical, spelling and punctuation errors. Each type of editing has its own complex and specific tasks, helping to ensure the writer's goal and the effectiveness of the work. The article is aimed at identifying the need for editing literary texts and its importance.

Keywords: *Stylistic editing, Compositional editing, Linguistic editing, Lexicon, Stylistics, Punctuation, Text structure, Effectiveness, Spelling*

INTRODUCTION: This article examines the main types of literary text editing - stylistic, compositional and linguistic editing. Editing a literary text is an important and complex process of literary work, editing a text is aimed at further improving the writer's work, eliminating its mistakes and shortcomings, and ultimately giving it an impact, aesthetic form and content. Literary text editing is divided into several types, each of which serves to perform specific tasks. In the process of writing a piece of fiction, its structure, style and language aspects require the main attention. These types of editing ensure that the text is highly expressive, flowing and aesthetically fluid. In stylistic editing, attention is mainly focused on lexical and stylistic elements, and in

3-GLOBAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH 2026

compositional editing, attention is paid to the arrangement and compatibility of parts of the text. In terms of language, editing means that speech expressions are correct, full and fluent.

THE MAIN PART: The main goal of stylistic editing is to ensure the stylistic integrity of the text. In this process, the writer's incorrect lexical and stylistic choices are corrected. For example, if the author describes a character with a professional or scientific appearance, then he should use words that are understandable and clear to the public. The main emphasis in stylistic editing is that each word, phrase and paragraph should correspond to the general style of the text, its content and the specific purpose of the writer.

Important elements of stylistic editing: Lexical and stylistic choices; Compatibility of words and their use; Descriptive methods; Speech emotional effects
Compositional editing is aimed at editing the structure, order and mutual arrangement of parts of the text. In this type, it is important to correctly divide the author's clear and precise thoughts into parts that complement each other. For example, the introduction, development, and conclusion of a story or novel should be consistent, and each scene should be consistent with each other. Objectives of compositional editing: Improve the order of the text; Strengthen the connections between the parts; Ensure the logical development of the story.

Linguistic editing - ensures that the text is clear, fluent, and understandable. This type of editing corrects the writer's language rules, incorrectly used words, and grammatical errors. Important aspects of linguistic editing are grammatical correctness, punctuation, word matching, sentence structure, and avoiding language overload. Objectives of linguistic editing: Ensure the grammatical correctness of the text; Check the correct use of punctuation and words; Make the text fluent and understandable
Editing a literary text is a complex and unique process, each type of which ensures that the text is clear, effective and aesthetically pleasing. The methods of stylistic, compositional and linguistic editing are interconnected and complement each other.

3-GLOBAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH 2026

Stylistic editing ensures the stylistic and lexical writing of the text, compositional editing ensures its order and parts, and linguistic editing ensures its adaptation to grammatical and linguistic rules.

Each type of editing serves to improve the text and adapt it to the writer's purpose. In this process, the editor should strive to preserve the original clarity of the writer, as well as make changes aimed at enhancing the overall impact of the text. Also, close cooperation between the editor and the writer during the editing process is one of the main factors in ensuring creative success.

CONCLUSION: Editing of artistic text is an integral and responsible process of literary creation, which plays a decisive role in the perfection of the work in terms of form and content. In the editing process, the idea, style and artistic solutions of the writer are not only fully expressed, but also are ensured to be conveyed to the reader in an effective, fluent and logical way.

Stylistic editing forms the artistic style, lexical richness and aesthetic content of the text. At this stage, word choice, phraseology, descriptive techniques, and stylistic devices are analyzed to ensure their appropriateness to the text. The author will have the opportunity to increase the level of influence while maintaining his style of speech. Compositional editing serves to control the internal structure of an artistic work, the connection between parts, and the orderly and logical development of the plot line. The correct organization of the balance, plot and time sequence in the introduction, climax and final parts of the work ensures artistic completeness.

Linguistic editing is aimed at ensuring grammatical correctness, adherence to spelling and punctuation rules, and the meaningfulness and clarity of word and sentence structure. This type of editing makes the text easy to read, understandable, and technically effortless.

In general, these three types of editing are closely related, and their joint and effective use turns the text into a complete work of art. The editing process, based on the harmony between the writer and the editor, literary culture, and critical thinking,

3-GLOBAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH 2026

makes the creative product more profound, effective, and meaningful. Editing is not just a matter of correcting errors, but also a process of shaping artistic thought, refining style, and enhancing creative results.

References:

1. Hamidov, K. K. (2021). Regarding the transference of metaphors in uzbek novels in Turkish translations. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(4), 200-205.
2. Xayrulla Hamidov. *Miad Hakimov – mohir tarjimon (monografiya)* ISBN: 978-9910-8970-0-9. 2025. Volume 1 Pages- 144
3. Mamajanova, Dildora. 2021. «HOW COVID-19 ENHANCED MY DIGITAL LITERACY: REFLECTIONS AND TIPS ON DIGITAL TEACHING TOOLS». *Журнал иностранных языков лингвистики* 2 (7). <https://fll.jdpu.uz/index.php/fll/article/view/2226>.
4. Khamidov, X. K., Bultakov, I. Y., Raxmanberdiyeva, K. S., Kasimova, S. S., & Sodiqova, S. B. (2024). Linguistic Expertise of Educational Literature: Analysis and Results. *Journal Power System Technology*, 48(4), 4017-4027.
5. Akramxodjaeva, D., Nasretdinova, M., & Abdullayeva, M. (2020). Translation of national events and concepts in fiction. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(2), 2984-2986.
6. Botirova, D. B., Abdullayeva, M. R., & Khaydarov, I. Y. Ra'no Anvarovna Khaydarova, and Shaxnoza Sharofovna Sharfova." *Social Psychological Features of the Process of Professional Stress in Pedagogical Activity.*". *Journal Power System Technology ISSN*, 1000-3673.
7. Nasretdinova, M. N., & Ruxshona, X. (2024). Methods of Analysizing New Words by Reading Texts. *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1, 229-232.
8. Nurmatov Yorkin Irkinovich, & Ernazarov Fakhritdin Tulkunovich. (2022). *THE CONCEPT OF PRONUNCIATION STYLE IN MODERN LINGUISTICS.* *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 1(7), 188–

3-GLOBAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH 2026

194. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646657>
9. Djampulatova, Nigora Mahmudovna. "Improving the Level of Communication Development of Students." *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement* 1.2 (2024): 180-185.
10. Alimbayeva, S. A., & Khusamiddinova, M. M. (2025). PRAGMATIC FACTORS AND THEIR ROLE IN TRANSLATION. SHOKH LIBRARY.
11. Saidakbarova, S. P., Mukhamedova, N. K., Jalolova, I. M., Mirabdullayeva, Z. O., & Akramkhodjayeva, D. A. (2024). The Role Of Speech Genres In The Communication Process. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 2500-2503.
12. Saodat Parxadjanovna Saidakbarova. UNDERSTANDING OF CODING SYSTEMS IN TEACHING AND TRANSLATING // ILM SARCHASHMALARI. URGANCH DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI .: - 5/2023. - bet 185
13. Teshaboyeva Ziyodakhon Qodirovna, & Qodiriy Mahzuna Shavkataliyevna. (2024). THE APPEARANCE OF VISUAL EXPRESSIONS' TRANSLATION INTO ENGLISH IN THE WORK "THE DAYS GONE BY" BY ABDULLA QODIRIY. Open
14. Access Repository, 10(1), 78–81. Retrieved from <https://oarepo.org/index.php/oa/article/view/3983>